

SOIL BIOPHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES UNDER DIFFERENT LAND
USES IN PORT HARCOURT METROPOLIS

By

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated soil biophysico-chemical properties under different land uses in Port Harcourt metropolis. Land use types are represented by Residential area (RS), Agricultural area (AG), Commercial area (CO), and Industrial area (IN). Random sampling using a soil auger was used to collect topsoil at a depth of 0-30cm; five soil samples from five points of each of the land use types were weighed(m/kg) and aggregated into a composite soil. Four composite soils collected were air dried, homogenized and sieved to pass through APHA, ASTM, and EPA for the standard biological, physical and chemical analyses using ANOVA for data analysis. The results showed that biological properties were significantly different across the different groups at $p > 0.005$. Total Organic Matter and Total Heterotrophic Bacteria in CO and IN are strongly affected by inappropriate land use and rapid urbanisation, reducing soil decomposers. The physical and chemical properties of soil were not significantly different among the different land uses. The availability of heavy metals in soil samples were arranged in this sequence of decreasing order as $Fe > Zn > Cu$, the amount Fe was found above regulatory limit of EGASPIN (Environmental Guidelines and Standards for the Petroleum Industry in Nigeria), NESREA (National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency) and FAO/WHO (Food and Agriculture Organization and World Health Organization) in all land use. The prevalence of heavy metals in CO was due to anthropogenic activity such as ore processing, upsurge in vehicular emission and unrestrained pattern of waste disposal. The depletion of Zn and Cu in AG is an input of poor farming methods, inadequate soil conservation and overlapping mixed land use. Therefore, increasing the vegetation in commercial areas will aid in replenishing degrading soil by increasing soil biological activities, and acceptable farming methods restore nutrients and essential metals like Cu and Zn for quality crop production.

KEYWORDS: land use, biophysico-chemical property, anthropogenic activity, urbanization

INTRODUCTION

Land use type threatens the pristine nature soil by decreasing the quality of public health, directly impacting biological diversity and diminishing ecosystem services (Foley et al., 2005; Ojo et al., 2022; IPBES, 2018). Population growth, commercialization and urban expansion have directly and indirectly contributed to the land use pattern that reflects human activities in geographical areas (Wali et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2019; Okwakpam, 2021; UNCCD 2024). Land resources are used to satisfy human needs like productions of crops,

shelter, recreation, commerce and religion, which determine the land use type of the region. Notwithstanding the necessity, human actions in the different land use type is putting the globe at risk by contributing to climate change with an increased rate of deforestation to build, increasing industrial waste generation and detrimental agricultural practices (UNCCD & PIK, 2024; IPCC, 2019). Libessart et al. (2021) and Xie et al. (2022) investigation revealed that the land use type influences soil pedogenesis and soil properties.

Soil properties are globally essential for the production of crops for food security, the provision of habitat for biodiversity support, maintenance of soil and environmental quality (Foley et al., 2005; Xie et al., 2022). These different ways of land use reflect on the properties of the soil, as they are closely linked. The study of Alamany et al. (2022) reported that different patterns of land use and their alterations in the Al-Jabal Al-Akhdar region of Libya affected the soil properties negatively. The pattern of land use affects soil biological, physical and chemical properties, which leads to fast degradation of soil, soil nutrients, reducing biodiversity and devaluation of the soil by erosion and increase litters. The research conducted by Xu et al. (2019) highlighted that the quality of soil is affected by anthropogenic forces to transform land use or harmful land use patterns that have been left unchecked for a long-time stimulates soil degradation and habitat fragmentation, thereby reducing the quality of the environment. The findings from Amare et al. (2023) showed that total nitrogen, available phosphorus, pH, Cation Exchange Capacity(CEC) and moisture contents in the soil have significantly declined across the different land use types investigated in Northwest Ethiopia. Likewise, Talmoures et al. (2022) and Li et al. (2025) stated that land use type influences the fractional distribution of soil particles by degrading the proportion of soil silt, clay and sand, which exacerbates soil loss, thereby causing erosion and flooding. From the different studies, it implies that the biophysico-chemical status of the soil reflects the level of soil degradation that is principal for its mitigation actions.

In Nigeria, various scientific report has revealed that rapid population growth, uncontrolled urban expansion and inadequate knowledge of their actions make up the land use system, which undermines soil properties. For example, these anthropogenic intrusions make the land vulnerable by declining biological activities and physiochemical properties of the soil, which facilitate soil loss (Bosah et al., 2013; Ufot et al., 2016; Joseph et al., 2019; Ojo et al., 2022; Okonofua et al., 2023). In addition, Jimoh et al. (2018) and Ota et al. (2024) reported that instability of soil properties are human induced with multifunctional land use types across different cities without a sustainable plan. Information about the statues of soil properties from different land use has become an increasing area of scientific research because of its significance in human health and land management, which is essential for safeguarding the value of ecosystem services and effective climate change planning.

Port Harcourt metropolis, after the discovery of crude oil experience continuous increase in population and urban expansion, which has caused overlapping land uses that are linked to several environmental issues by scholars such as Wali et al. (2018), Okwakpam (2021), Kamalu et al. (2022) and Otene et al. (2023). The land use type in Port Harcourt metropolis is multifunctional for residential, agricultural, commercial and industrial areas. Oil spillage and indiscriminate discharge of spent crude from industrial land use areas; increased litter and indiscriminate dumping of household waste in residential land use areas; road construction, deforestation for building offices and crowding in commercial land use areas; deforestation and encroachment on wetland for subsistence farming in agricultural land use areas. These aforementioned land use actions undermine its ecological integrity by deteriorating the quality of soil properties, availability of lethal heavy metals and perturbation of the biosphere, which changes the climate of the area, increasing flooding and fragmentation of habitat by reducing vegetative cover (Douglas, 2017; IPCC 2019; Asmare et al., 2023; Li et al., 2025). Metal availability in the Port Harcourt metropolis is connected to run-off from dumpsites because of a lack of proper waste management, which led to modification of the soil property (Edori & Kpee, 2017; Wanjala et

al., 2019; Iyama & Edori, 2021; Amadi et al., 2024). Therefore, it's important to assess the soil biophysico-chemical properties under different land use types in Port Harcourt metropolis for sustainable management of the land resource.

METHODOLOGY

- **Study Area**

This research was carried out in Port Harcourt Metropolis, which is primarily a combination of two Port Harcourt City Local Government Area (Phalga) and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area (Obalga), which is also extended towards Choba and Rukpoku, all in Rivers State, Nigeria (Nwankwoala & Omunguye, 2013; Okwakpam & Mark, 2021). The main types of soil in Port Harcourt metropolis are commonly clayey and sandy, which are impacted by the different hydrological regime which are saline deltaic plain and freshwater inland zones that support a wide range of biodiversity (Ibim et al., 2020; Wali et al., 2018). Its vegetation comprises tropical forest with abundant mesophytes and swamp forest having abundant halophytic species, which have alternating seasons, a 4-month dry season and a prolonged rainy season that lasts for 8-months with a relative humidity of 80% and temperature ranging from 24- 29 °C throughout the year.

As time progressed with the discovery of crude oil in old River State (now Bayelsa), the traditional economic occupation of the people has changed to rapid industrialization with dependence on crude oil exploitation and exploration activities, rapid urban growth with real estate sprawling due to increase in population as several international oil companies have their headquarters in the Port Harcourt metropolis and other human activities, has invigorated environmental degradation and change the land use pattern.

- **Site Selection**

Four different locations in Port Harcourt metropolis were selected for this study based on 4 land uses, which included Residential Area (RS), Industrial Area (IN), Commercial Area (CO) and Agricultural Area (AG) (Fig.1), reflecting the major land use in Rivers State. In selecting the site of study, highways and water bodies were avoided, but maintained a perfect distance that covers 90km² (Fig. 2). RSs are located 4°49'30"N and 7°0'30"E (Fig. 2), an area that has a gentle slope evident of gully erosion with demolition building and construction. INs are areas with moderate water table, coordinates 4°48'30"N and 7°2'30"E (Fig. 2), with land modified due to clusters of industries such as oil serving firms, breweries, car assembling firms and automobile workshops contributing urban waste and hydrocarbon spillages. AGs were secondary forest covered with *Telfairia occidentalis*, *Manihot esculenta*, *Dioscorea* sp., *Elaeis guineensis*, *Alchornea cordifolia*, *Zea mays* and leafy vegetables with a straight soil surface form, evidence of sheet erosion, no drainage facility, 4°54'30"N and 7°1'30"E (Fig. 2), with dense population, enhanced tillage, deforestation and exploited land resources. COs are within the coordinates of 4°50'30"N and 6°58'30"E (Fig. 2), comprising local markets, motor parks, and abattoirs, whose operations increases wastes accumulations with visible litter, ca ongested multi-functional zone with visible degradation and overpopulated.

Fig.1: Geographical Map of the Study Area

Fig. 2: Location map of the Area Studied

• Soil Sampling and Method of Collection

Each of the land use sites (RS, IN, AG and CO) were sampled by the establishment of a set of 10m by 10m plots, which was further reduced to 5 sub-plots (1mx1m) from which soil samples were collected with the aid of a soil auger at a depth of 0-30cm. Five soil samples were collected from each of the sampling sites in RS, IN, AG and CO and weighed (g/kg) distinctively to determine the particle size of the soil. After quantifying their particle size, 5 soil samples from each of the different sites were composited for each land

use (Miswan et al., 2023). Temperature was determined in situ using a mercury-in-glass thermometer, then properly bagged and transported to the laboratory for analysis.

- **Methods of Laboratory Analysis of Soil**

The samples of soil taken to the laboratory were air-dried, gently grinded, sieved through 2.0mm mesh and stored at 27°C pending analysis. pH was determined ex situ with APHA 4500-H+P test method. Soil color determined through APHA 2120C test method. Total porosity was estimated using EPA2000 method. Moisture content was measured using standard test method. Total Organic Matter (TOM) and Total Organic Carbon (TOC) were tested using ASTM D2974 (Fawole & Ogo, 2014). Available Phosphorus (TP) and Total Nitrogen (TN) were determined using APHA 4500 P.E and APHA 4500-NC procedures, respectively. Effective Cation exchange capacity (ECEC) was determined using ASTM D7503-10. Total Heterotrophic bacteria were determined using standard microbial technique through APHA 9215B. The soil samples were further digested to analyze for heavy metals using APHA 3111C method for Fe, Cu, Zn and APHA 3500B for Mg by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) as described by Allen et al. (1974).

- **Statistical Analysis**

The mean of the different land use types was calculated using Microsoft excel while ANOVA was used to check for a significant difference. SPSS (version 25) was used for ANOVA.

RESULTS

The results for the particle fraction of the sampled soil from the different land use types RS, AG, CO, and IN are shown in Table 1. The soil textural fraction of sand, silt and clay significantly varied with land use types (Table 4.1). The mean value of sand increases in RS, IN and CO, and CO. This significance is due to construction activity in the area. The higher mean value of clay fraction in AG than other land use types support the fact that agriculture promotes further weathering processes (Fig. 4.1, 4.3).

Table 1: Particle fraction(distribution) of Sampled Soils

Land Use	Depth	Sampling Points	Clay (g/kg)	Silt (g/kg)	Sand (g/kg)	Texture
RS	0-30cm	PT1	178	30	458	Sandy loam
		PT2	189	28	573	Sandy loam
		PT3	201	60	423	Sandy clay loam
		PT4	228	45	605	Sandy clay loam
		PT5	211	28	60	Clay loam
		Mean	201.4	38.2	423.8	
AG	0-30cm	PT1	762	20	119	Clay loam
		PT2	534	24	141	Clay loam
		PT3	692	15	121	Clay loam
		PT4	744	12	112	Clay loam
		PT5	672	18	122	Clay loam
		Mean	680.8	17.8	123	
CO	0-30cm	PT1	128	40	352	Sandy loam
		PT2	121	60	453	Sandy loam

		PT3	142	60	352	Sandy loam
		PT4	105	72	213	Sandy loam
		PT5	132	60	321	Sandy loam
		Mean	125.6	58.4	338.2	
IN	0-30cm	PT1	109	80	564	Sandy loam
		PT2	85	100	632	Sandy loam
		PT3	132	65	451	Sandy loam
		PT4	192	45	658	Sandy loam
		PT5	121	21	325	Sandy loam
		Mean	127.8	62.2	526	

N/B: PT1=Point 1, PT2=Point 2, PT3=Point 3, PT4=Point 4, PT5=Point5.

The values of TOM of the sampled soil are 1.12%, 2.48%, 3.04% and 2.43% were obtained in RS, AG, CO and IN, respectively (Table 2). Total Heterotrophic Bacteria (THB) of the sampled soils are 5.5×10^7 cfu/g, 4.2×10^7 cfu/g, 1.2×10^7 cfu/g, and 2.2×10^7 cfu/g were obtained in RS, AG, CO and IN, respectively.

The colors of differs across the different land use, having Brownish, Brownish, Brownish Gray and Brownish that signify pore surface (Table2). The Brownish Gray found in CO reflects the deeper horizon due to the presence of insoluble Fe^{2+} and Mn^{2+} (Athur & Okae-Anti, 2022). Moisture content (MC) ranged from 9.00-20.00%, showing a decrease of CO (16.24%) > AG (11.85%) > IN (10.19%) > RS (9.96%) in Table 2. IN has the highest total porosity, and CO has the lowest total porosity.

pH detected in the sampled soils ranged from 5.61 to 6.31, which were comparatively acidic. The concentrations of Total Organic Carbon (TOC) variation decreased in the order of CO (1.76 %) > AG (1.45%) > IN (1.40) > RS (0.65%), whereby CO had a higher concentration than the other land use areas due to high litter accumulation. Total Nitrogen (TN) decreased slightly among different land uses, showing a decreasing sequence of IN (59.22 mg/kg) > RS (55.14 mg/kg) > CO (53.87 mg/kg) > AG (46.69 mg/kg) in Table 2. Available Phosphorus (Av.P) fluctuated at a range from 3.66mg/kg to 5.27mg/kg within the different land use types. Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) of the soils varied greatly among different land uses due to spatial geography of Port Harcourt. The values of CEC varied as 69.67med/100g (RS), 37.66med/100g (AG), 364.0med/100g (CO) and 73.20med/100g (IN) land use types (Table 2).

The concentration of heavy metals found in the RS soil sample are arranged in sequence of decreasing order as Fe (3468mg/kg) > Mg (162mg/kg) > Zn (38.3mg/kg) > Cu (6.05mg/kg). The concentration of heavy metals found in the AG soil sample is arranged in decreasing order of Fe (2513mg/kg) > Mg (33.73mg/kg) > Cu (6.90mg/kg) > Zn (0.01mg/kg). The concentration of heavy metals found in the CO soil sample is arranged in decreasing order of Fe (7810mg/kg) > Mg (280.8mg/kg) > Zn (227.6mg/kg) > Cu (27.25mg/kg).

Table 2: Concentration of some selected biophysio-chemical properties of Sampled Soils in comparison to Regulatory standard

Parameters	Land Use Type				Recommended Limits		
	RS	AG	CO	IN	FAO/WHO	NESREA	EGASPIN
pH	6.31	5.61	5.88	5.80	6.0-7.5,	6.5 - 8.5	5.5-9.5
Temperature, °C	28.5	24.2	25.8	23.3	-	-	36.24
Colour	Brownish	Brownish	Brownish Gray	Brownish	-	-	-
Total Porosity, %	34	34	32	56	-	-	-
Moisture Content, %	9.96	11.85	16.24	10.19	-	-	-
Cation Exchange Capacity, meq/100g	69.67	37.66	346.0	73.20	-	-	-
Total Nitrogen, mg/kg	55.14	46.69	53.87	59.22	-	-	-
Available Phosphorous, mg/kg	5.27	3.66	5.08	4.71	-	-	-
Total Organic Carbon, %	0.65	1.45	1.76	1.40	-	-	-
Total Organic Matter, %	1.12	2.48	3.04	2.43	-	-	-
Total Heterotrophic Bacteria, CFUg-1	5.5×10 ⁷	4.2×10 ⁷	1.2×10 ⁷	2.2×10 ⁷	-	-	-
Iron, mg/kg	3,468	2,513	7,810	4,218	5,000	5000	5000
Magnesium, mg/kg	162	33.73	280.8	229.9	-	-	-
Zinc, mg/kg	38.3	<0.01	227.6	41.15	50 - 300	100 - 300	140
Copper, mg/kg	6.05	6.90	27.25	15.55	36 - 100	20 - 100	36

* *EGASPIN* (Environmental Guidelines and Standards for the Petroleum Industry in Nigeria); *NESREA* (National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency); *FAO/WHO* (Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and World Health Organization)

Statistical significance when $p=0.05$ was used to evaluate the variation of soil bio-physiochemical properties on the land use type. The soil physical and chemical property analyzed to determine variations in the different land use types show that the *F-value* is lower than the *F-critical* at 0.05 significance (Table 3). On the other hand, the biological properties indicate that the calculated *F-value* is higher than the *F-critical* at 0.05 significance (Table 3). According to the ANOVA test, state that there is no significant variation in the soil physical and chemical properties under different land use in Port Harcourt Metropolis, except for the biological properties, which significantly vary across the different land use types (Duman et al., 2023).

Table3: ANOVA analysis of different soil properties on different land Use

Land Use Tye Soil Properties	RS	AG	CO	IN	F-cal.	F-val.	Sig.
	(S ²)	(S ²)	(S ²)	(S ²)			
Biological	0.627	3.075	4.621	2.952	9.276628	10.127296	0.05
Physical	288.960	245.311	124.188	1049.278	9.2766	0.6509	0.05
Chemical	288.960	245.311	124.188	1049.278	3.008	0.278	0.05

Fig 3: mean weight soil textural fractions

Fig 4: mean weight of composite soil of different land use

Fig 5: heavy mental concentration of sampled soil.

Fig 6: Cation Exchange(meq/100g) and pH concentration of sampled soil.

Fig 7: Total Nitrogen (TN), Available Phosphorus (AP) and Total Organic Carbon (TOC) concentration of sampled soil.

DISCUSSIONS

- **Physical properties of the soil**

The variation of land use in the study area, particle fraction, where sand was recorded high in IN and CO, clay dominated AG and a varying proportion of clay and sand in RS. A similar study conducted by Amadi et al. (2024) elsewhere in Rivers State reported that land use effect textural distribution of sand, silt and clay. The varying textural classes in RS could be attributed to land encroachment by real estate firms to solve the problem of overpopulation, as most primitive agricultural areas are converted to other land uses, which significantly affects the texture of the soil, making the area susceptible to flooding, like the CO and IN area, with fine dominance of fine soil particles. This is consistent with the findings of Akintola et al. (2022) and Kamalu et al. (2022). The soil colour was similar among the different land uses except for the brownish grey colour in the CO, which translates to the high concentration of insoluble heavy metal Fe (Ufot et al., 2016; Joseph et al., 2019; Ogazie et al., 2022).

The lowest (32%) total porosity in this present study is under CO land use, which indicates the level of human activities that reduce clay content, causing flooding and land degradation due to reduced storage capacity and high compartment particularly in Rumuwoji and Nkpolu-Oroworoko Markets (Edori & Iyama, 2017; Ikati & Peter, 2019). On the other hand, IN had the highest (56%) total porosity reflect adequately structured soil without compaction that safeguard waterlog as observed in Trans-amadi and Oginigba. This result is consistent with the research conducted by Jemal and Tesfaye (2020) in the Gurage zone of Southern Ethiopia.

The moisture content varies across different land uses, with CO having the highest (16.24%) value due to less evaporation with respect to shading from the kind of infrastructure and buildings in the area. This result conforms with the findings of Edori and Iyama(2017) in certain commercial Abattoirs in Port Harcourt. Although the level of moisture content in AG can be attributed to the dominance of clay soil, which have high capacity to hold water and supports a greater diversity of flora than sandy soil (Jemal & Tesfaye, 2020; Amadi et al., 2024).

- **Chemical properties of the soil**

The high value of pH RS observed was slightly acidic basic which tends to be neutral as there is leaching of nutrients and an increase in the accumulation of waste. This outcome inclines to the findings of Amadi et al. (2021) conducted in Rivers State indicating a relatively lower acidic pH values 5.61, 5.80 and 5.88 under AG, IN and CO, respectively. The high acid content in soil in AG area reflects the assimilation of decomposed leaf litter, discharge of acid organic residue and high nutrient cycle by availability of vegetations which contributes to soil acidification. The finding is in line with the report from Edori and Iyama (2017) and Ikati and Peter (2019). Prior research conducted in industrial areas of Port Harcourt meteropolis by Eyetan and Ozabor(2021) revealed that the soils are acidic due to oil pollution, with negligence in handling oil spillage and indiscriminate discharge of petroleum waste.

Cation exchange capacity (CEC) is a summation of nutrient ions (Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}) essential for plant development and soil chemical stability. According to Ewunetu et al. (2025), high CEC indicate availability of cation nutrients; if they are low, there is a reduction of nutrient ions, revealing intense human interference, deterioration of soil fertility and decline in ecosystem health. CEC value in this current study was higher compared to the discoveries by Ikati and Peter (2019) and Amadi et al. (2024). The lowest value of CEC in AG is due to low pH value and high clay content. This finding is consistent with the findings of Abile et al. (2025) that the agricultural pattern of land use lessens cation exchange in the soil.

The statues of soil nutrients like TN, Av. P and TOC slightly vary across the different land uses in this study. The high concentration of TN (59.22mg/kg) was found under IN, which is attributed to the intense discharge of industrial waste that contains nitrogenous compounds (NO_3^- , NH_4^+ and Urea). This level of TN in IN was higher compared to the previous study carried out by Eyetan and Ozabor (2021) in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

The highest concentration of Av. P (5.27mg/kg) was observed under RS, whereas the lowest amount of Av. P (3.66mg/kg) was documented in AG. The textural dominance of clay in AG has stimulated the fixing of phosphorus, thereby reducing its availability in the soil. This finding is supported by Alovisi et al. (2020) in Brazil. The amount of Av. P within this study, ranging 5.27-3.66 mg/kg, is very low compared to what is recorded in the research conducted by Joseph et al. (2019) and Abile et al. (2025), but similar to the report by Amadi et al. (2024) in Nigeria. The amount of TOC recorded in this study is low compared to the result reported by Edori and Iyama (2017) and Iyama and Edori (2021), which implies that urban and infrastructure expansion over time has distorted the ecosystem stability and reduced plant biological activities. The highest amount (1.76%) of TOC was recorded in CO, while the lowest (0.65%) was under RS, which translates to the intense anthropogenic disturbance making the area susceptible to flooding and erosion (Akukwe, 2014; Joseph et al., 2019). The level of TOC in AG (1.45%) reflects local activities such as intense cultivation, clearing of trees and proliferation of pollutants in the soil during burning (Akintola et al., 2022; Ewunetu et al., 2025).

Heavy metals were at high levels under CO in this study, which reflects the impact of intense human activities in different markets, which enhances land degradation. Likewise, an investigation carried out around a selected commercial area in Port Harcourt by Edori and Kpee (2017) discovered that Fe was the most dominant heavy metal in the soil. On the other hand, the lowest level of heavy metal was observed under the AG. The outcome of the research carried out by Ghorbani et al. (2015) affirmed that land used for agriculture was often less contaminated with heavy metal which supports the findings of the study. The concentration of Fe was higher than other heavy metals such as Zn and Cu in all land use types evaluated (Fig.5). All the land use type assessed except for CO has a concentration of Fe that is found within the safe limit of FAO/WHO, NESREA and EGASPIN. This implies that the high level of Fe in CO is due to proliferation of waste metal scraps, local ore smelting, litters and inadequate waste management has contributed to the high concentration of Fe in soils endangering public health through biomagnification of toxin in the ecological network (Department of Petroleum Resources, 2002; Nouri & Haddioui, 2016; Douglas, 2017; Akintola et al., 2022). The level of Zn found in RS and IN was below the permissible limit of FAO/WHO, NESREA and EGASPIN, except for the concentration recorded under CO. The implication is that land use patterns in CO enhance the proliferation of toxic metals that endanger the biotic component of the ecosystem (Eyetan & Ozabor, 2021). Although the recorded concentration of Zn (<0.01 mg/kg) in AG designates Zn deficient soil owing to the intensive farming without adequate management in the study area.

This outcome supports the finding of Ogazie et al. (2022) that established that cultural farming techniques by local farming have an impact on the chemical nutrients of agricultural soil. Despite the toxicity posed by high concentrations of Zn, it is essential to plant at a safe concentration as Zn acts as a co-enzyme and supports plant growth when found within the required threshold (Iyama et al., 2022), thus the need to sustainably manage the farm practice. Likewise, the concentration of Cu in RS, AG and IN is below the required limit of 20mg/kg to 100mg/kg prescribed by FAO/WHO, NESREA and EGASPIN, but CO had a concentration of 27.25mg/kg of Cu, which is within the permissible threshold. The depletion of heavy metals that is beneficial at a limit concentration could affect the quality of the soil and affect plant development, especially in agricultural soils. This finding is consistent with previous reports from Nwankwoala et al. (2016), Wanjala et al. (2019) and Iyama et al. (2022).

- **Biological Properties of the soil**

The selected biological properties, such as TOM and THB, found in the land uses were very significant ($p < 0.05$). The level of TOM was higher (3.04) with the lowest presence of THB in CO, implying that high availability of heavy metals and low pH recorded in CO inhibited bacterial activities and reduced their

capacity to break down organic matter, which lessens the quality of the soil. Contrarily, the amount of TOM was lowest (1.12%) in RS with the highest concentration of THB, which is attributed to an increase in microbial activity by decomposing the organic matter to strengthen the soil fertility. The finding from the study aligns with the report from Nwakwoala et al. (2016) and Ojo et al. (2022). This suggests that anthropogenic activities impede the abundance of microbial communities in the soil, which limits the level of decomposition of organic matter in the soil, thereby decreasing pH level and other nutrients. The variation of the availability of THB and TOM shows a complex land use process that diminishes the soil quality. According to Mhete et al. (2020), pollution and disturbance regimes from different patterns of land impact on the biological property by influencing the microbial diversity and the level of organic matter. The study conducted by Nwakwoala et al. (2016) reveals that the availability of THB in soil contributes to the stability and fertility of the soil. Similarly, Ojo et al. (2022) highlighted in their research conducted at the National Centre for Genetic Resources and Biotechnology (NACGRAB) in Ibadan that increase availability of microorganisms stimulates biological activities by safeguarding soil structural stability that can withstand the forces of erosion that degrade land over time. Though the decline observed in some land use area indicate the need for urgent action to improve the status of the soil.

Bosah (2013) emphasised the need for environmental education as its negligence indicates how people use natural resources, which move the climate towards extremes. This study is show that most people are not aware of the damage their actions cause to the sustainability of land resources. It is therefore recommended that private institutions and governmental agencies integrate action in creating awareness, revegetation campaigns and support research.

CONCLUSION

Land use alters the accepted ecological balance as it alters the biophysicochemical properties that decline the soil stability. This research provided the current status of the influence of different land use pattern such as RS, IN, CO and AG, on the biological, physical and chemical properties of soil in the study area. The study discovered that the chemical and physical properties of the soil were not statistically significantly different under the different land use, but the biological property varies significantly ($p > 0.005$). This study established that land use for CO was highly impacted by anthropogenic action, indiscriminate waste disposal and an inadequate waste management system, making the soil properties, such as pH, and CEC enhances the concentration of Fe above the safety standard, which affected the availability of THB. On the other hand, Zn were observed to be deficient in AG, which relates to the farming system employed by the farmers. There is an ardent need for consistent monitoring of farming techniques to improved concentration of Zn in AG as the decline will impact the plant growth and development. For sustainable land management, this study recommends that the government, through research institutions and agencies, systematically monitor the anthropogenic activities around different land which increase pollutants in the environment to protect public health. Also, the study suggests that the Ministry of Agriculture and Environment should monitor farming activities to mitigate nutrient depletion and essential metals that affect plant growth and development. The information obtained from this research can be a guide to facilitate further studies.

References

- Abile, H., Fituma, K., & Mammo, S. (2025). Impact of land use types on selected soil physicochemical parameters in the case of Liben Jawi district, Ethiopia. *Scientific Reports*, 15(1), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-12784-z>
- Akintola, O. O., Abodunrin, E. K., Odeyale, O. C., Falana, A. R., Ogunbanjo, A. R., & Adeniran, T. (2022). Influence of land use types on physical and chemical properties in oba hill forest reserve, Iwo, south-western Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Sciences and Environmental Management*, 26(7), 1307-1377. <https://doi.org/10.4314/jasem.v26i7.18>

Akukwe, T.I. (2014). Determinants of Flooding in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Nigeria. *OSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*,19(11), 64-72.

Alawamy, J. S., Balasundram, S. K., Mohd. Hanif, A. H., & Teh Boon Sung, C. (2022). Response of Potential Indicators of Soil Quality to Land-Use and Land-Cover Change under a Mediterranean Climate in the Region of Al-Jabal Al-Akhdar, Libya. *Sustainability*, 14(1), 162. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14010162>

Allen, S.E., Grimshaw, H.M., Parkinson, J.A. & Quarmby, C. (1974). Chemical analysis of ecological materials. Oxford: Blackwell Scientific (8) second edition.

Alovisi, A. M., Cassol, C. J., Nascimento, J. S., Soares, N. B., Da Silva Junior, I. R., Da Silva, R. S., & Da Silva, J. A. (2020). Soil factors affecting phosphorus adsorption in soils of the Cerrado, Brazil. *Geoderma Regional*, 22, e00298. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2020.e00298>

Amadi, N., Yabrade, M., Nsan-Nicholas, O. H., & Gbosidom, V. L. (2024). Physiochemical properties of soil from waste Dumpsites within Choba, Alakahia and Rumuosi communities in Akpor, Rivers State, Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Sciences and Environmental Management*, 28(7), 2217-2225. <https://doi.org/10.4314/jasem.v28i7.36>

Arthur, A. & Okae-Anti, D. (2022) Variations in Soil Physico-Chemical Properties as Influenced by Landuse in a Toposequence. *Journal of Geoscience and Environment Protection*, 10, 98-121. doi: [10.4236/gep.2022.108008](https://doi.org/10.4236/gep.2022.108008).

Asmare, T. K., Abayneh, B., Yigzaw, M., & Birhan, T. A. (2023). The effect of land use type on selected soil physicochemical properties in Shihatig watershed, Dabat district, northwest Ethiopia. *Heliyon*, 9(5), e16038. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e16038>

ASTM (2014). ASTM D2974-14 Standard Test Methods for Moisture, Ash, and Organic Matter of Peat and Other Organic Soils; ASTM International: West Conshohocken, PA, USA.

Bore, G., & Bedadi, B. (2015). Impacts of Land Use Types on Selected Soil Physico-Chemical Physico Chemical Properties of Loma Woreda, Woreda Dawuro Zone, Southern Ethiopia. *Journal of Science, Technology and Arts Research*, 4(4), 40–48. <https://doi.org/10.4314/star.v4i4.6>

Bosah, V. O. (2013). Environmental education in Nigeria: Issues, challenges and prospects. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(15), 159-167. <https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2013.v4n15p159>

Department of Petroleum Resources (2002). Environmental guidelines and standards for the petroleum industry in Nigeria (EGASPIN) Abuja, Nigeria: Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Resources. 314

Douglas, I. (2017). “Ecosystems and human well-being.” in Encyclopedia of the anthropocene (Elsevier), 185–197. doi:10.1016/B978-0-12-809665-9.09206-5

Duman, A., Yildirim, C., Tufekcioglu, M., Tufekcioglu, A., & Satiral, C. (2023). Variation in Certain Soil Properties Based on Land Use Type, and Elevation in Arhavi Sub-Basin, Artvin, Turkiye. *Sustainability*, 15(11), 9114. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15119114>

Edori O. S. & Kpee F. (2017). Index models assessment of heavy metal pollution in soils within selected abattoirs in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. *Singapore Journal of Scientific Research*, 7(1), 9-15. <https://doi.org/10.3923/sjsres.2017.9.15>

Edori, O. S. & Iyama, W.A. (2017) Assessment of Physicochemical Parameters of Soils from Selected Abattoirs in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. *J Environ Anal Chem*, 4(194), 1-5. doi:10.41722380-2391.1000194

Ewunetu, T., Selassie, Y. G., Molla, E., Admase, H., & Gezahegn, A. (2025). Soil properties under different land uses and slope gradients: Implications for sustainable land management in the Tach Karnuary watershed, Northwestern Ethiopia. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 13, 1518068. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2025.1518068>

- Eyetan, T. & Ozabor, F. (2021). Oil spills deposits effect on soil physicochemical properties in Port Harcourt metropolis: Implication for agricultural planning. *Journal of Management and Social Science Research*, 2(1/2), 45 – 58. DOI 10.47524/jmssr.v2i1.46
- Fawole, M.O. & Oso, B.A. (2014). Characterization of Bacteria; laboratory manual of microbiology. 4th edition, Spectrum Book limited, Ibadan, Nigeria. 24-33.
- Foley, J. A., Defries, R., Asner, G. P., Barford, C., Bonan, G., Carpenter, S. R., Chapin, F. S., Coe, M. T., Daily, G. C., Gibbs, H. K., Helkowski, J. H., Holloway, T., Howard, E. A., Kucharik, C. J., Monfreda, C., Patz, J. A., Prentice, I. C., Ramankutty, N., & Snyder, P. K. (2005). Global consequences of land use. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, 309(5734), 570–574. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1111772>
- Fu, D., Xu, Z., Wu, X., Zhao, L., Zhu, A., Duan, C., Chadwick, D. R., & Jones, D. L. (2021). Land use effects on soil phosphorus behavior characteristics in the eutrophic aquatic-terrestrial ecotone of Dianchi Lake, China. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 205, 104793. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2020.104793>
- Ghorbani H., Moghadas, H N. & Kashi, H. (2015). Effects of land use on the concentrations of some heavy metals in soils of Golestan Province, Iran. *Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology*. 17, 1025-1040
- Ibima, A. T., Francisb, A. & Iwalehin, E. A. (2020) An Assessment of the Condition of Fishes in the Amadi Creek, Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research*, 50(2), 154-165
- Ikati, W.C & Peter, K.D. (2019). Variations Of Soil Properties as Influenced by Land Use and Soil Depth in Coastal Plain Sands of Port Harcourt, Southern Nigeria. *Int'l Journal of Agric. And Rural Dev.*, 22(1), 4000-4005.
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). (2019). *Climate change and land: An IPCC special report on climate change, desertification, land degradation, sustainable land management, food security, and greenhouse gas fluxes in terrestrial ecosystems*. IPCC. <https://www.ipcc.ch/srccel/>
- Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES). (2018). *The IPBES assessment report on land degradation and restoration*. IPBES Secretariat. <https://www.ipbes.net/es/node/17873>
- Iyama, W. A., & Etori, O. S. (2021). Comparative Study of Organic Parameters of Soils from Three Selected Universities in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Nigeria. *European Journal of Applied Sciences*, 9(1),21-34
- Iyama, W. A., Okpara, K., & Techato, K. (2022). Assessment of Heavy Metals in Agricultural Soils and Plant (*Vernonia amygdalina* Delile) in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Nigeria. *Agriculture*, 12(1), 27. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture12010027>
- Jemal, K., & Tesfaye, H. (2020). Soil physico-chemical property characterisation along with different land use system in Gurage zone, southern Ethiopia. *Mod. Chem*, 8(3), 40-47.
- Jimoh, R., Afonja, Y., Albert, C. & Amoo, N. (2018). Spatio-temporal urban expansion analysis in a growing City of Oyo Town, Oyo State, Nigeria using remote sensing and Geographic Information System (GIS) tools. *Int J Environ Geoinformatics* 5(2):104–113.
- Joseph P.O., Ojochegebe O.F., Okonfor A.S. & Faith, K. C. (2019). Impacts of Different Land Use on Some Selected Soil Physicochemical Properties in Federal Polytechnic Idah, Kogi State, Nigeria. *South Asian Res J Agri Fish* 1(1)17-22
- Kamalu, O. J., Ogio, V. & Ikiriko, M. E. (2022). Evaluation Of Soil Quality Under Different Land Use Types in the Coastal Plain Sands of Niger Delta. *Journal of Global Ecology and Environment*, 15(4), 37–44. <https://doi.org/10.56557/jogee/2022/v15i47615>

- Li, J., Liu, S., Yang, D., Suo, F., Yu, Y., Wang, Z., & Liao, Q. (2025). The Impact of Land Use Types on the Soil Erosion Resistance in the Arid Valley Region of Southwest China. *Agriculture*, 15(4), 386. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture15040386>
- Libessart, G., Franck-Néel, C., Branchu, P., & Schwartz, C. (2022). The human factor of pedogenesis described by historical trajectories of land use: The case of Paris. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 222, 104393. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2022.104393>
- Mhete, M., Eze, P. N., Rahube, T. O., & Akinyemi, F. O. (2020). Soil properties influence bacterial abundance and diversity under different land-use regimes in semi-arid environments. *Scientific African*, 7, e00246. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2019.e00246>
- Miswan, M. S., Hamdan, R., Azman, M. H. A., Ab. Aziz, N. A., & Siddiqui, Z. (2023). Determination of Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium in Soil and Plant Due to Husbandry Farming in Parit Rasipan Drainage System. *International Journal of Sustainable Construction Engineering and Technology*, 14(2), 197-204. <https://publisher.uthm.edu.my/ojs/index.php/IJSCET/article/view/13839>
- Nouri, M., & Haddioui, A. E. (2016). Assessment of metals contamination and ecological risk in ait Ammar abandoned iron mine soil, Morocco. *Ekológia (Bratislava)*, 35(1), 32-49. <https://doi.org/10.1515/eko-2016-0003>
- Nwankwoala, H., Youdeowei, P. & Daka, E.(2016). Physico-Chemical, Heavy Metal and Microbiological Concentrations in Soil and Water Samples Around Veritas University Campus, Obehie, Southeastern Nigeria. *The International Journal of Earth & Environmental Sciences*, 1(1).1-6
- Nwankwoala, H.O. & Omunguye, M. L. (2013).Geophysical Investigation for Groundwater in Borokiri and Eastern-Bye Pass Areas of Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *Pacific Journal of Science and Technology*. 14(1),524-535.
- Ogazie, C. A. Ochekwu, E. B & Agbagwa, I.O. (2022). Influence of farming systems practices on physicochemical properties of soils in wet and dry season in University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *GSC Advanced Research and Reviews*,11 (02), 089–101
- Ogbuokiri, M., Okujiagu, D., & Opara, K. (2025). Groundwater Quality Assessment in Parts of Igwuruta and Environs, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *Engineering Research Journal*, 5(2), 31-47. <https://www.openjournals.ijaar.org/index.php/erj/article/view/1123>
- Ojo, A., Aliku, O., Aladele, S., Oshunsanya, S., Olubiyi, M., Olosunde, A., Ayantayo-Ojo, V., & Alowonle, A. (2022). Impacts of land-use types on soil physical quality: A case study of the national centre for genetic resources and biotechnology (NACGRAB), Nigeria. *Environmental Challenges*, 7, 100510. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envc.2022.100510>
- Okonofua, E., Ogbomida, E., Emeribe, C., Beckely Anichie, & Emeribe, O. (2023). Effect of land use types on soil properties in Benin City, Nigeria. *Tropical Environment, Biology, and Technology*, 1(2), 94-109. <https://doi.org/10.53623/tebt.v1i2.324>
- Okwakpam, I. O. & Mark, E. O. (2021). Spatio- Temporal Land Use Dynamics of Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, 5 (9), 569-573.
- Okwakpam, I. O. (2021). Quality of residential-neighbourhood environment of Port Harcourt city local government area of Rivers State. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(26).
- Ota, H. O., Mohan, K., Udume, B. U., Olim, D. M., & Okolo, C. C. (2024). Assessment of land use management and its effect on soil quality and carbon stock in Ebonyi state, southeast Nigeria. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 358, 120889. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.120889>

Otene, B., Thornhill, I., & Amadi, J. (2023). A comparison of the water quality and plankton diversity of the Okamini Stream to the freshwater systems within the New Calabar River catchment, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *African Journal of Aquatic Science*, 48(1), 97–104. <https://doi.org/10.2989/16085914.2022.2155102>

Tahmoures, M., Honarbakhsh, A., Afzali, S. F., Abotaleb, M., Ingram, B., & Ostovari, Y. (2022). Fractal Features of Soil Particles as an Indicator of Land Degradation under Different Types of Land Use at the Watershed Scale in Southern Iran. *Land*, 11(11), 2093. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11112093>

Ufot, U., Iren, O. & Njoku C. (2016). Effects of land use on soil physical and chemical properties in Akokwa area of Imo State, Nigeria. *Int. J. Life Sci. Sci. Res.*, 2(3), 273–278.

United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD), & Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK). (2024). *Stepping back from the precipice: Transforming land management to stay within planetary boundaries*. UNCCD. <https://www.unccd.int/news-stories/press-releases/planetary-boundaries-confronting-global-crisis-land-degradation>

Wali, E., Phil-Eze, P.O., Nwankwoala, H.O. (2018). Saltwater – freshwater wetland ecosystem and urban land use change in Port Harcourt metropolis, Nigeria. *Earth Science Malaysia*, 2(1), 01-07. <https://doi.org/10.26480/esmy.01.2018.01.07>

Wanjala, M.P. Odokuma, L., Etela, I & Ramkat, R. (2019). Assessment of Soil Metals Status in parts of Rivers State, Nigeria. *J. Appl. Sci. Environ. Manage.*, 23(3) 545-550.

Xu, L., Chen, S. S., Xu, Y., Li, G., & Su, W. (2019). Impacts of land-use change on habitat quality during 1985–2015 in the Taihu Lake Basin. *Sustainability*, 11(13), 3513.